

GitHub - Research

* Required

1. Email *

2. Name *

3. Email to receive the gift card *

General Info

4. Gender: How do you identify? *

Mark only one oval.

Male

Non-binary

Woman

Prefer not to answer

Other: _____

5. What's your age group? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 20 years
- 20-25
- 26-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- Above 50

6. What's your highest qualification? *

Mark only one oval.

- High-School
- Graduate degree
- Post graduate degree (Masters, MBA)
- Doctoral degree

7. What 's your major? *

8. Please include your GitHub profile link: *

Specific Info

9. How many years of experience do you have as a software developer? *

10. When have you started contributing to Open Source Software projects? *

11. How can you describe your current role in the OSS project? *

12. What are the last projects that you contributed/maintained? *

13. What are your areas of expertise? (e.g, programming, testing, design, etc) *

14. In OSS projects, how did you choose tasks that fit your expertise? *

15. What advice do you recommend for newcomers (students), when they have to identify skills from GitHub tasks? What information should they look at? *

16. When you analysed the issues, how did you extracted the skills identification from GitHub issues? Please try to describe the steps you took to extract the skills. *

17. Which issues from the categories below do you think are more difficult to identify?
Categories: (Database, Debugging, External Libraries, Operating infrastructure, Program comprehension, Programming concepts, Programming language, Project architecture, Project specific concepts, Testing) *

18. Can you recommend anybody else from your project we should invite to help us in this study? (Please, provide name and email). *

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